

COMPARISON OF VERB TENSES IN THE UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Abstract: This article examines structural discordances in English and Uzbek by providing specific examples of differences and similarities between the two languages. We will study how to employ grammatical categories of verbs in both languages in this post [1].

Keywords: English, Uzbek, verb, suffixes, order, numeral, nouns, grammatical transformation.

Introduction

The classification of word groups in modern English and Uzbek is determined by the following characteristics of words, a) lexical and lexico-grammatical meanings, b) the generality of morphological forms for words belonging to a particular group, c) the role of words in speech. Word groups are also called lexical-grammatical categories of words because their lexical and grammatical forms are taken into account when dividing words into groups [Chomsky 1957: 416]. For example, all words in the horse category refer to the subject name. It should be noted, however, that not all horses need to be subject. Although some words do not denote an object, they are still used in place of an object. For example, love in English, place of joy, friendship in Uzbek, happiness and so on.

Uzbek Verbs

Learning the Uzbek Verbs is very important because its structure is used in every day conversation. The more you master it the more you get closer to mastering the Uzbek language. But first we need to know what the role of Verbs is in the structure of the grammar in Uzbek.

Uzbek verbs are words that convey action (bring, read, walk, run), or a state of being (exist, stand). In most languages a verb may agree with the person, gender, and/or number of some of its arguments, such as its subject, or object.

Grammar Tips:

- Present Tense

In Uzbek, present tense is formed according to the following rule:

Verb-moq (ending of the indefinite form) + yap + personal endings. For example the verb qilmoq (do): qil-moq=qil + yap + personal endings:

Men (I) qilyapman (am doing)

Biz (we) qilyapmiz (are doing)

Sen (you) qilyapsan (are doing)

Siz (you) qilyapsiz (are doing)

U (he, she, it) qilyapti (is doing) Ular (they) qilyaptilar (are doing)
These endings can help you a lot, because with them you can conjugate most of verbs into the present tense, you only need the stem of the verb, for example the stem of (o'ynamoq: to play) is (o'yna).

- Past Tense

In Uzbek as well as in English the simple past tense (imperfect) is used to describe past events. The endings for the **past tense verbs** are:

Men (I) qildim (did) Biz (we) qildik (did)
Sen (you) qilding (did) Siz (you) qildingiz (did)
U (he, she, it) qildi (did) Ular (they) qildilar (did)

So just take any verb **stem** and add it to the endings above, for example our previous verb o'ynamoq (to play), its stem is "o'yna", plus the endings above becomes **Men o'ynadim** (I played).

- Future Tense

Forming of the future in Uzbek is very easy. If the **stem** of the verb ends in **-a**, then **-y** is added after that **-a**, and the personal endings. If the **stem** of the verb ends in other letter, you use **-a**, and then the personal endings.

Men (I) qilaman, ishlayman (will do; will work) Biz
(we) qilamiz ishlaymiz (will do; will work)
Sen (you) qilasan ishlaysan (will do; will work) Siz (you) qilasiz ishlaysiz
(will do; will work)
U (he, she, it) qiladi ishlaydi (will do; will work) Ular
(they) qiladilar ishlaydilar (will do; will work)

English verbs

Past, present and future are the three main types of tenses.

Past tense

The past tense is used to describe an activity or an event that has happened in the past or a past state of being and needs to include a time marker for when the event or action took place.

Structural formula:

Subject + verb (2nd form) + object.

Examples:

- We met *yesterday*.
- He bought a new laptop *last week*.

Present tense

The simple present tense or present tense is one of the most basic tenses in English. We use present tense to talk about something that is currently going on, something that is habitually performed, or a state that generally or currently exists.

Structural formula:

Subject + verb (s/es) + object.

Examples:

- She *lives* in Spain.
- Bob *drives* a taxi.

Future tense

The future tense is a verb tense used to describe an event or action that has not yet happened and is expected to happen in the future. Structural formula, Subject + shall/will+ verb (s/es) + object.

Example:

- He *will* be here soon.

Now that we have understood the three main types of tenses, communicating in English with a native English speaker will become easier. But to make communication in English easier and simpler, we need to learn more about tenses.

Each category has its own morphological forms of words, which form morphological paradigms and are associated with known grammatical categories

Conclusion

These are also vivid examples of structural discordance of English and Uzbek set verb tenses. So, grammatical system of any language plays a great role in its functioning. To render appropriate meaningful content in a correct grammatical construction needs perfect knowledge and mastering grammatical peculiarities of both languages. The most difficult points in this aspect are: syntactical structures, pronouns, article, gender, tenses and other grammatical categories

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